

Decentralized intelligence in the service of heterogeneous swarms

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Abstract. Swarm systems are characterized as highly heterogeneous and dynamic. The development of heterogeneous swarm systems represents a complex process that requires substantial effort. Ensuring correctness and efficiency is especially challenging in this domain. In this paper, we report on the work in progress carried out in the context of the Horizon Europe project TaRDIS (Trustworthy and Resilient Decentralized Intelligence for Edge Systems), emphasizing the advances on framework supporting machine learning modeling primitives. More specifically, we describe the main properties of the Flower-based federated learning tool developed for the needs of the project. The project aims to ease the complexity of building applications for swarms by proposing a language-independent event-driven programming paradigm that provides distribution abstractions and decentralized machine learning primitives. In combination with a dedicated toolbox, the novel programming paradigm reduces the complexity of the development of applications for swarm and decentralized distributed systems. The proposed capabilities are being validated in four real-world use cases within the project, which are provided by high-impact industrial partners.

Keywords: heterogeneous swarms · machine learning · federated learning · edge systems

1 Introduction

A distributed system [1] represents a collection of independent components, connected and communicating over a network, in order to solve a common goal. They are challenging to develop and maintain by their nature. In swarm systems [2], it becomes even more demanding, due to the high level of heterogeneity and dynamic aspects of the system. The idea behind swarm intelligence is to develop computational solutions for complex problems. It was inspired by the collective behaviour of social swarms in nature, e.g. ant colonies. These systems are

decentralized and self-organizing. Various challenges arise while developing this kind of a system [3]. Although the elements of a swarm are connected using a network, a set of issues related to communication protocols, orchestration, coherence, system coordination, decision making and other important aspects may appear.

1.1 Positioning and contributions

The foundations for swarm-based systems can be already found in works from the 20th century, where some conceptual elements of such systems emerge [4]. Later, during the early 2000s, the idea finds its use in swarm robotics and multi-agent systems first [5]. Eventually, the idea evolved to its modern form, where swarm systems and applications finds their use in various complex domains. In [6], swarm-based optimization methods are explained, while focusing on the way to model these decentralized, self-organizing systems aimed to solve complex optimization problems. A variety of papers related to real-world applications of swarm systems emerged early, e.g. [7], where the application of swarm principles in the design of a decentralized robotic system for warehouse automation was presented. The topic is of great interest nowadays, which inspired a wide range of applications and innovations. In [8], a distributed swarm learning for IoT at the edge was proposed. The collaboration of a large number of self-organized IoT devices into a decentralized swarm computing system, with collaborative intelligence, was explored in [9]. The body of scientific literature on this topic is extensive. One of the main challenges is to try to overcome the complexities that arise during swarm system development and maintenance.

There are numerous initiatives aimed at solving problems related to data and knowledge exploitation in decentralized systems, while striving to reduce complexity. The OASEES [10] (Open autonomous programmable cloud apps & smart sensors) project is focused on developing a swarm programmability framework for edge devices, with decentralized and secure features, while utilizing AI/ML accelerators. Another important effort is represented through the OpenSwarm [11] project, that aims to offer energy-aware swarms of collaborative and distributed smart nodes. Additionally, the P2CODE [12] (Programming Platform for Intelligent Collaborative Deployments) project focuses on emphasizing the potentials of edge intelligence, by exposing an IoT-to-edge-to-cloud compute continuum, in a secure and trusted manner, through an open platform. The SMARTEDGE [13] project is also dedicated to tools for edge intelligence, by working on semantic low-code programming tools, while aiming at dynamic integration of decentralized edge intelligence at runtime in a secure, reliable manner.

TaRDIS tends to identify common programming abstractions. It strives to define a system architecture, while identifying and following the requirements for the development environment and defining the evaluation methodology. It defines a programming model, but also an API and an IDE that enable access to the developed tools and services. The TaRDIS development approach provides guidelines on integrating TaRDIS in existing software development methodologies.

Furthermore, it develops formal analyses for reliability, security and soundness of a heterogeneous swarm system. The machine learning component in TaRDIS offers support for decentralized learning and inference through AI/ML primitives, but also for AI-driven planning, deployment and orchestration, as well as for novel lightweight ML techniques for resource-constrained devices. TaRDIS also focuses on the development of decentralized, distributed membership and communication primitives and data replication solutions. It tends to build a monitoring infrastructure in order to support system reconfiguration. All these efforts are meant to be consolidated and implemented in the context of four industrial use cases. In this overview, we focus on describing the main features of the Flower-based federated learning tool developed to support the AI/ML primitives of TaRDIS.

2 Machine learning modeling primitives

The development of decentralized machine learning solutions represents an important component of the proposed TaRDIS framework. It contributes to the objectives through three different dimensions: creating a decentralized learning and inference framework supporting AI/ML primitives, developing an AI-driven planning, deployment and orchestration framework and providing a library of lightweight and energy efficient ML techniques. This paper provides an overview of a tool, developed as a decentralized learning and inference framework, the Flower-based FL (federated learning) tool, which corresponds to the first ML-related objective.

In order to fulfill the need for a federated learning approach that offers solutions for different tasks, while supporting different devices, we have chosen the Flower[14] framework as a base for our FL tool. Flower is an open-source FL framework, that is easily adaptable to heterogeneous FL device setups. Its extensible and flexible nature enables defining various ML models and build custom FL strategies. It makes the process of building FL solutions easier, by providing the core components of a FL system. The framework architecture is based on the Server and Client abstractions, with the Strategy abstraction positioned in between to guide the federated learnign process. By default, bidirectional gRPC streams are used as communication protocol, which enables message exchanges serialized in binary formats.

The Flower-based FL tool represents a synthesis of three building blocks: a data preparation component, a FL model training component and an inference and evaluation component. The central part is the FL model training component, as it provides a set of federated machine learning solutions and enable model training, in a simple manner. Regarding FL algorithms, the tool currently supports federated averaging, i.e. FedAvg [15] and personalized FL with Moreau envelopes, i.e. pFedMe [16]. FedAvg is a commonly used and popular approach to consolidate the local results from the participating clients. Its main disadvantage is poor performance guarantee, when data heterogeneity is present. This affects the usability of the obtained global model on the local clients. In

order to compensate this obstacle, we provide a personalized solution, that uses a mixture of global and local models. This approach is well known as personalized FL with Moreau envelopes (pFedMe) [16]. We also have implemented a novel variation of pFedMe, named pFedMe_new, that takes a new batch in each inner iteration, where pFedMe takes a batch and performs inner iterations on it. We evaluated these approaches through the task of image classification on the FashionMNIST [18] data set. The tests showed the expected outcomes, where pFedMe performs better than FedAvg in a heterogeneous setup, by producing a robust global model. Moreover, the accuracy of the global model can become even higher for pFedMe_new than for pFedMe. We illustrate this in Fig. 1, where we show the global accuracies achieved for FedAvg, pFedMe and pFedMe_new (for more details, see D5.1 [19]).

Fig. 1. Global model accuracies from FedAvg, pFedMe, pFedMe_new. Source: D5.1 [19]

The Flower-based FL tool also contains a solution for the task of anomaly detection, build upon the HUNOD (Hybrid UNsupervised Outlier Detection) [20] method. This approach integrates two complementary ML methodologies: clustering using K-means and representational learning using autoencoders. The developed FL solution was tested on the MetroPT-3 [23] dataset. The results show an accuracy value up to 94.08%.

Besides the described approaches, there are a few ongoing FL approaches under development, that will be integrated into the tool. There are some methodological advances, that can be easily incorporated to the tool implementation, according to the needs. These are: a new method for one shot clustered learning [17], advances in the context of clustered [21] and robust distributed learning [22].

The main advantage of the developed Flower-based FL tool is that it supports the developer during the process of setting the training up, so that no FL expertise is needed in order to train a model. This contributes to accessibility and user-friendliness of FL approaches, encouraging non-expert users to utilize

them. By providing a set of FL algorithms in a decentralized Flower framework, the tool meets the necessary project requirements.

The Flower-based FL tool is accessible in two manners: via command-line interface, or via graphical user interface (GUI). The interface is intuitive and provides streamlined and flexible workflow. It allows to select a new model, or to load a pre-existing model, which can be convenient in addressing specific needs. The customization of the federated learning process allows also training parameters tuning, including adjusting the number of training rounds, the number of clients, batch sizes, but also setting up the number of local epoch on clients, learning rate settings, momentum values setup for the optimizer, client participation rates setup and task-specific settings, e.g. number of classes in classification tasks. This process enables a straightforward way for even non-expert users, to optimize their FL models for particular needs.

Fig. 2. The GUI for setting up the training in the Flower-based FL tool.

The GUI of the tool for setting up the training process is shown on Fig 2. The first assignment is to select a task that needs to be solved, followed by a dataset selection. Then, the user can choose to train a new model or use a pretrained one. The tool then offers a selection of models to be used. The provided choices depend on the previous selections, so the tool prevents setting up non-applicable or meaningless combinations of choices. This is an important feature to support the user during making these choices inside a safe environment. When the training is finished, the tool provides the option to view graphical representations of the results. The type of these outcomes depends on the chosen setup, i.e. model and algorithm. For example, for the setup shown on Fig. 2, the tool shows accuracy

and loss plotted over training rounds. The tool aims to provide ease of use, by abstracting some complex aspects of FL setup. This makes FL more accessible to a broader audience of users. The tool is easy to expand, so that new FL solutions can be easily incorporated by expert users. We plan to complement the current list of supported models and algorithms. We also plan to work on some additional features, as possible model compaction for resource-constrained devices, providing recommendations based on sample data and client selection optimization.

3 Conclusion

The process of the development of decentralized, heterogeneous swarm applications introduces a set of challenges and complexities. Heterogeneous swarm-based systems are widely applicable and deployable in diverse settings. In this paper, we provided an overview of the ongoing project TaRDIS, that aims to provide decentralized intelligence solutions for edge systems. We provided a brief overview of the literature and current state of the art regarding similar initiatives. The main focus of this paper was to provide an overview of a ML component of TaRDIS, the Flower-based FL tool. We discussed the main advantages and possibilities that the tool offers. We also highlighted the main aspects of the tool that will be refined and adapted in the upcoming period. Although an integral part of the TaRDIS toolbox, the tool can also be utilized and expanded individually for diverse FL setups.

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References

1. G. Coulouris, J. Dollimore, T. Kindberg, and G. Blair. 2012. *Distributed Systems: Concepts and Design*. 5th ed. Addison-Wesley, Harlow, England.
2. Bonabeau, E., Dorigo, M., and Theraulaz, G. 1999. *Swarm Intelligence: From Natural to Artificial Systems*. Oxford University Press, New York, NY.
3. M. Brambilla, E. Ferrante, M. Birattari, and M. Dorigo. 2013. Swarm robotics: A review from the swarm engineering perspective. *Swarm Intelligence*, 7, 1 (2013), 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11721-012-0075-2>
4. G. Beni and J. Wang. 1989. *Swarm Intelligence in Cellular Robotic Systems*. In *Proceedings of the NATO Advanced Workshop on Robots and Biological Systems (Tuscany, Italy, June 26–30, 1989)*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 703–712.
5. Sahin, Erol. (2005). *Swarm Robotics: From Sources of Inspiration to Domains of Application*. *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.*. 3342. 10-20. [10.1007/978-3-540-30552-1_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-30552-1_2).

6. X. S. Yang, “Nature-Inspired Metaheuristic Algorithms,” Luniver Press, 2010.
7. Peter R. Wurman, Raffaello D’Andrea, and Mick Mountz. 2007. Coordinating hundreds of cooperative, autonomous vehicles in warehouses. In Proceedings of the 19th national conference on Innovative applications of artificial intelligence - Volume 2 (IAAI’07). AAAI Press, 1752–1759.
8. Yue Wang, Zhi Tian, Xin Fan, Zhipeng Cai, Cameron Nowzari, and Kai Zeng. 2024. Distributed Swarm Learning for Edge Internet of Things. *Comm. Mag.* 62, 11 (November 2024), 160–166. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.003.2300610>
9. L.C. de Biase, G. Fedrecheski, P. Calcina-Ccori, R. Lopes, M. Zuffo. 2023. Swarm Computing: The Emergence of a Collective Artificial Intelligence at the Edge of the Internet, *Edge Computing*, IntechOpen, Rijeka. Chapter 5, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.110907>
10. OASEES: Open Autonomous Programmable Cloud Apps & Smart Edge Sensors. Coordinated by National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos,” Horizon Europe Grant No.101092702, Jan.2023–Dec.2025, <https://oasees-project.eu/>
11. OpenSwarm: Orchestration and Programming ENergy-aware and Collaborative Swarms With AI-powered Reliable Methods. Coordinated by Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et Automatique (INRIA), Horizon Europe Grant 101093046, Jan. 2023–Apr. 2026, <https://openswarm.eu/>.
12. P2CODE: Programming Platform for Intelligent Collaborative Deployments over Heterogeneous Edge-IoT Environments. Unisystems Luxembourg Sarl, Horizon Europe Grant 101093069, 2023–2025, <https://p2code-project.eu/>.
13. SMARTEDGE: Semantic Low-code Programming Tools for Edge Intelligence. Coordinated by Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni (CNIT), Horizon Europe Grant No. 101092908, Jan. 2023–Dec. 2025, <https://www.smart-edge.eu/>.
14. Daniel J. Beutel, Taner Topal, Akhil Mathur, Xinchu Qiu, Javier Fernandez-Marques, et al. FLOWER: A FRIENDLY FEDERATED LEARNING FRAMEWORK. 2022. hal-03601230
15. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y. Arcas, “Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data,” in Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, A. Singh and J. Zhu, Eds., ser. Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, vol. 54, PMLR, 20–22 Apr 2017, pp. 1273–1282. [Online]. Available: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/mcmahan17a.html>
16. C. T. Dinh, N. Tran, and J. Nguyen, “Personalized federated learning with moreau envelopes,” in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. Balcan, and H. Lin, Eds., vol. 33, Curran Associates, Inc., 2020, pp. 21 394–21 405. [Online].
17. Aleksandar Armacki, Dragana Bajovic, Dusan Jakovetic, Soumya Kar. A One-shot Framework for Distributed Clustered Learning in Heterogeneous Environments. *IEEE Trans. Sig. Proc.* 2024.
18. Xiao, H., Rasul, K., & Vollgraf, R. (2017). Fashion-MNIST: a Novel Image Dataset for Benchmarking Machine Learning Algorithms. arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.07747. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1708.07747>
19. TaRDIS consortium. 2024. Deliverable D5.1: Initial report on distributed AI and AI-based orchestration. TaRDIS project. Available: https://www.project-tardis.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/101/2024/07/TaRDIS_D5.1-Final.pdf
20. M. Savic, J. Atanasijevic, D. Jakovetic, N. Krejic. Tax evasion risk management using a Hybrid Unsupervised Outlier Detection method. *Expert Syst. Appl.* 193, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.01033>

21. A. Armacki, H. Sharma, D. Bajović, D. Jakovetić, M. Chakraborty, S. Kar. Distributed Gradient Clustering: Convergence and the Effect of Initialization. Asilomar conference on signals, systems and computers, October 27-30, 2024
22. D. Bajović, D. Jakovetić, S. Kar, M. Vuković. Tackling heavy-tailed noise in distributed estimation: Asymptotic performance and tradeoffs. Telecommunications Forum, TELFOR, November 26-27, 2024
23. B. Veloso, R.P. Ribeiro, P. M. Pereira, J. Gama: The MetroPT dataset for predictive maintenance. Scientific Data 9, no. 1, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01877-3>